

HOW UMI-TECHNOLOGIES ENDORSE STEM LEARNING

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The study investigates the effect of UMI-technologies on pupils' interest in STEM education and STEM related careers. UMI is the abbreviation of Ubiquitous Computing, Mobile Computing, and Internet of Things. The study involved ca. 600 13 – 16 years of age pupils in five countries (Finland, Greece, Ireland, Italy, and Norway). The data was gathered in an online questionnaire developed in the study and the data was analyzed statistically in SPSS. This study focus on findings in the Finnish case. The descriptive findings show that new technological solutions do not self-evidently support interest growth in STEM education and STEM careers, but may operate as a basis for it. Especially the practical technical problems generate frustration and decrease the interest towards STEM learning which in turn effects on their generic views on technology emphasized teaching, learning, and careers. It seems that there is a delicate balance on when the practical technical challenges motivate and endorse the learner to try more and when they demotivate and cause frustration. Based on the experience gained in this study, the practical technical challenges related to the introduction of new ICT solutions in education needs to be noted and should not be anticipated. More study is needed in the field.

Keywords: ICT enhanced teaching and learning, communities of practice, STEM education

INTRODUCTION

New technologies such as ubiquitous computing, mobile computing and the Internet of Things (collectively named as UMI) provide new possibilities for teaching and learning. These technologies are so modern and powerful that can be both an educational means and end, thus fostering innovation and supporting promising scientific careers. The broad aim of the study is to investigate the impact of UMI technologies in education. The study is part of a larger international survey and EU founded project among five countries (Finland, Greece, Ireland, Italy and Norway).

In this EU project, the UMI technologies are put in practice to enhance the level of science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) education and at the same time make STEM careers attractive prospect for young girls and boys. Inspired by Weiser's idea (Weiser, 1991; 1998), an UMI integrated educational scenarios were designed for lower secondary school. The themes of the scenarios were selected on the basis that would increase the pupils', especially girls, interest both to STEM and UMI.

The starting point for scenarios design was ROSE study (Lavonen et al., 2005) which investigated the 15 years of aged pupils' ideas about the relevance of the science education. Based on the study such contexts as environmental education and biology were implemented. The other important viewpoints were the close connection to the student's everyday life and improvement of the student's thinking skills. Several themes were discussed and based on the project need, the professional interest and the expertise of the research team, the study of bathroom lights, the bacterial growth and the plant watering systems were selected. The themes are in close connection to students' everyday life, to environment and to the sustainable future which are according to the ROSE study such contexts that interest the female learners more and hopefully overcome their low interest towards the technology context.

The study seeks to find answer the following question: Does UMI-technologies bring added value to the classroom STEM education in pursuit of increase pupils' interest to STEM education and STEM careers?

METHOD

The UMI-emphasized pilot course was launched in the Viikki Teacher Training School of the University of Helsinki. The pilot phase comprised one pilot group of lower secondary school pupils (N=17) and larger follow-up study group (N=94). The research team comprised a researcher from the University of Helsinki

and three teachers from the Viikki Teacher Training School. The researcher was in charge of the research design and the teachers were in charge of the design and implementation of the educational scenarios.

The pupils to the course were chosen on the basis of their interest, free will and availability at the time. The pupils in the school are selected based on the place where they live. The school is evaluated similar to other local suburban school regarding on the facilities to teach mathematics, and sciences and the teachers' educational background (Kupiainen et al. 2009). Thus, the school in this project can be considered as typical lower secondary school where the great majority of pupils have the white middle class background.

The data on pupils' interest and motivation on STEM education and STEM was collected by the online questionnaire developed in the study. Data gathering focused on pupils' interest and attitudes towards STEM education and careers. The data was analyzed in SPSS and Excel statistically. Descriptive data was achieved in pilot study, statistically sound results is able to present in the actual ESERA conference as data gathering in the ongoing larger studies are finished.

The questionnaire comprises two questions about the pupils' background (gender and age), 26 statements about the UMI emphasized STEM education, one open-ended question about the teaching and one open-ended question where pupils could make general comments about the questionnaire and the instruction during the course. The questionnaire was administered to 17 pupils of which 14 answered the questions, 9 boy and 4 girl pupils and 1 did not wanted to answer the question. Ten pupils were aged 15, one was aged 16 and three pupils did not answer the question.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The pupils were asked, among others, their opinions and experiences concerning the satisfaction, enjoyment and performance concerning on the activity and the device itself. The pupils could express their views on how the activity could be improved and they could give free form feedback about the activity. As for the subject matter and type of activity, the analysis focuses on the study of the bathroom lights.

In general, the results show medium level enjoyment and interest towards the activity, ie. the study of bathroom lights. The pupils' satisfaction on average with the activity was 3.79 and their enjoyment with the activity was on average 3.82 in seven point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree). The scores are somewhat above the medium. The easiness of the activity was evaluated to the satisfactory level and achieved the average score 4.16. The pupils also evaluated their own work during the activity by two thematic areas. The one explored how much control the pupils believed they had over the activity and the other how they would characterize their performance with the activity while being involved in the digital application. The pupils evaluated their control over the activity rather high 4.46 which made it the second highest average score among the questions. Also their own estimate about their performance was on the good level achieving the average score of 4.15. These corroborate the finding that the pupils graded the easiness of the activity similarly achieving the average score 4.16 as mentioned above. The usefulness and pupils' intention to use the activity in the future achieved at good average scores. The usefulness was evaluated to level 4.61 which made it the highest score. However, the pupils' intention to use the activity in future was not as high, achieving the average score of 4.07, which made it the second lowest average score among the questions.

The pupils evaluated the work with the UDOO/Arduino itself as well. The highest score 4.00 was achieved in the question that asked the pupils' opinion about how thrilling the artefact is, but the results of many other questions corroborate the finding that the practical was somewhat above the medium level as it came to the enjoyment and funniness of the practical. The lowest average score 2.64 were achieved in the questions that elaborated the pupils' intention to use the UDOO/Arduino in the future.

To sum up, the pupils could perceive the connection of the activity and its relevance to everyday life, but did not regard the activity as itself especially enjoyable. The pupils' comments to the open-ended questions corroborate the finding, but also illuminate the reasons behind the issue. One pupil argues that the UDOO/Arduino itself is too slow that generates negative feeling. Another pupil argues that the number of pupils in the class could be smaller and a third one that the teacher did not have enough time for them. These

are the things that are not directly connected with the activity itself, but the learning environment. On the other hand, the pupils seemed self-confident carrying out the practical activity and the usefulness of the activity reached the highest score. These might indicate some sort of hidden potential of the activity and while the teachers are gaining more experiences carrying out the activity with the pupils, the pupils' experiences might turn in to more positive by the same token. We wish to emphasize that the findings are highly tentative due the small number of the respondents.

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